

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11568692>

INCREASING TOURISTIC POTENTIAL OF KARAKALPAKSTAN USING MARKETING TOOLS: THE CASE OF THE “MIZDAKHAN-SACRED AND MYSTERIOUS PLACE” FESTIVAL

Mariya Bekimbetova

PhD student, Tashkent state university of economics

ABSTRACT

In recent years, the touristic potential of Karakalpakstan has significantly increased, moving beyond the historical focus on Tashkent. According to Kim Tatyana (2021), most tourists previously visited Uzbekistan for business, concentrating their visits in Tashkent. This trend left other regions underdeveloped in terms of tourism infrastructure and services. The Presidential Decree No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022, aims to boost tourism across Uzbekistan, including Karakalpakstan, by enhancing infrastructure, creating jobs, and promoting sustainable tourism.

Karakalpakstan, known for its potential in eco and pilgrimage tourism, is currently in a development phase. The festival "Mizdakhon - Sacred and Mysterious Place," held in May 2024, highlighted the region's cultural heritage and unique historical sites. The event featured international scholars, including Nobel Laureate Professor Raekwon Chung, who emphasized the role of community engagement and sustainable practices in transforming Karakalpakstan into a popular tourist destination.

To further enhance Karakalpakstan's touristic appeal, effective marketing strategies such as storytelling, festivals, art, and digital campaigns are crucial. These tools can increase visibility, drive economic growth, preserve cultural heritage, and engage local communities, ensuring the sustainable development of the region's rich cultural assets.

Key words: *tourism, development, marketing, marketing tools for tourism development, tourism potential, pilgrimage tourism.*

Tourism development in Uzbekistan

In recent years, the touristic potential of Karakalpakstan, as well as other parts of Uzbekistan, has seen a positive increase. It is important to note that previously, only Tashkent, the capital of Uzbekistan, was the primary destination for visitors. According to Kim Tatyana (2021), who studied the purpose of traveling to Uzbekistan, findings show that most people (80%) in previous years visited Uzbekistan primarily for work trips. Consequently, their touristic route was centered in Tashkent, which was the most

visited by tourists, leaving other regions relatively unnoticed. This concentration of tourists in Tashkent can be attributed to most recreational and touristic service providers being located and centered there. As a result, the touristic potential of other parts of Uzbekistan remained underdeveloped, with the level of service provision in these areas not fully matured.

According to the Presidential Decree No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, titled "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," there are several strategic goals aimed at accelerating the development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates. This decree includes 16 goals under the priority direction "Rapid Development of the National Economy and Ensuring High Growth Rates." Additionally, the "Travel Across Uzbekistan" program aims to increase the number of local tourists to over 12 million and the number of foreign tourists visiting the country to 9 million. This program includes these main directions:

Implementing Barrier-Free Tourism Infrastructure: This involves widely implementing accessible tourism infrastructure in the main tourist cities of the country.

Doubling Employment in the Tourism Sector: By 2026, the goal is to double the number of people employed in the tourism sector, reaching 520,000 individuals.

Developing Tourism and Cultural Heritage Infrastructure: The state program aims to effectively use over 8,000 cultural heritage sites by developing related infrastructure.

Creating Additional Tourist Zones and Resorts: Projects worth \$300 million will be implemented in the Zomin, Forish, Baxmal districts, and the "Aydar-Arnasoy" lakes system, creating 25,000 jobs.

Transforming Samarkand into the "Gateway to Tourism": Over the next five years, tourism services in Samarkand are expected to increase tenfold, providing employment for 40,000 people. In 2022, the Samarkand tourism center, including the "Eternal City" historical complex, and necessary infrastructure were established.

Developing Ecotourism in Karakalpakstan and the Aral Sea Region: A specific program for developing ecotourism in these regions is being implemented.

This presidential decree aimed at developing the touristic potential of other parts of the country, including Karakalpakstan, has brought positive waves of tourism to these areas. Tourism and touristic services have started gaining popularity in Karakalpakstan. The phases of tourism development can be categorized into four stages:

Opening and Initial Development Phase: This stage is characterized by the slow growth of tourists visiting the area, minimal interaction with the local population, a lack of services, and very low usage of resources and infrastructure.

Growth and Development: At this stage, the number of tourists begins to increase, and there is the organization of specific service-providing companies to offer touristic and recreational services.

Maturation: In this phase, tourism becomes well-established, with significant improvements in infrastructure and services. Local businesses and communities begin to see tangible economic benefits from tourism.

Stabilization and Possible Decline: During this stage, tourism growth stabilizes. If not managed properly, there can be a decline in tourist numbers due to over-saturation, environmental degradation, or a decrease in service quality.

Referring to the above phases and governmental statistics we can state that tourism in Karakalpakstan is currently at a development stage with the identification of its main tourism types. Karakalpakstan has significant potential in both eco and pilgrimage tourism, which need to be promoted globally using effective marketing tools like storytelling. Recently, on May 17-18, 2024, the Karakalpak Tourism Committee, in partnership with Tashkent State University of Economics and the Administration of Khodzheyli District, organized a festival called “Mizdakhan - Sacred and Mysterious Place.” The festival aimed to increase the touristic potential of Karakalpakstan by unveiling such hidden treasures to the world and making these places popular. Festivals like this help convey the true essence of these sites to tourists, allowing them to experience the local culture personally.

At this festival, professors and academicians from seven different countries, including Nobel Prize Laureate Professor Raekwon Chung, were present. Professor Chung shared the story of the successful green transformation of Suncheon City in South Korea, drawing parallels to the Aral ecological catastrophe in Karakalpakstan. He stated that places like Suncheon or Karakalpakstan could become popular tourist destinations for both local and foreign visitors once the right formula for success is implemented. He emphasized that solving such ecological catastrophes requires the engagement of people, businesses, and the government. These three stakeholders form a triangle, and the formula for success won't work if full responsibility is placed solely on the government or businesses; people must also be willing to take responsibility and commit to making their homeland a safe, clean, and prospering place. Other guests, including the representative of UNESCO in Uzbekistan, Sara Noshadi, shared their inspiring talks and experiences, highlighting the importance of ecological prosperity alongside economic development.

To introduce guests to the history of Karakalpakstan, particularly the historical artifacts of Khodzheyli, they were presented with the story of the Mizdakhan Apocalypse Clock, in the heart of the Khodjeyli district, stretches the mysterious ruin known as “Rejep Qalpe”. According to the legend, every year, one brick falls from the walls of the ancient structure, as if marking a peculiar countdown, unknown to both man and nature. And the Mazlymhan Suliw monument, which carries a deep and sad

story. The Mazlymhan Suliw monument, built around 13-14th century, is unique because part of it is located underground. This monument was constructed for the daughter of a ruler who wished to choose her own husband through a competition. The first round of the competition required suitors to bring her a red rose that lights up in several colors under the sun. A young architect in love with Mazlymhan Suliw created this flower from crystals and won the first round. During the competition, Mazlymhan Suliw also fell in love with the architect and wanted him to win. The second round involved constructing the most beautiful castle for her, with the winner set to live there with her. However, an evil minister, who wanted to marry Mazlymhan Suliw himself, changed the third round's conditions, making it seem as if she wanted the winner to throw himself from the heights of the palace to prove his love. The young architect, saddened but deeply in love, threw himself off the palace, believing it was Mazlymhan Suliw's wish. When she discovered the truth, she couldn't bear the pain of losing her beloved and also threw herself from the palace. They were buried together within the palace by her father.

During the festival, this sad yet unique story was compared to Shakespeare's Romeo and Juliet. It was suggested that the story be shared globally through art forms such as ballets or musical festivals, as music and art transcend language barriers. This approach is particularly relevant in Karakalpakstan, where many locals face language barriers in retelling their stories. In summary, the strategic initiatives and engaging storytelling events like the "Mizdakhan - Sacred and Mysterious Place" festival play a crucial role in promoting Karakalpakstan's touristic potential, enhancing its visibility on the global stage, and contributing to the sustainable development of the region.

Recommendations on further development:

Accordingly, we can say that Karakalpakstan's tourism is currently in its development stage, with significant potential in eco and pilgrimage tourism. Recent efforts, such as the festival "Mizdakhan - Sacred and Mysterious Place," have begun to unveil the region's hidden treasures to the world, leveraging festivals and storytelling to convey the local culture and historical significance to tourists.

To further popularize Karakalpakstan's touristic heritage, several marketing tools and strategies can be implemented:

Storytelling: Creating compelling narratives around historical sites like the Mizdakhan Apocalypse Clock and the Nazlymhan Suliw monument can attract tourists by offering them a rich cultural experience. Stories like the tragic love story of Nazlymhan Suliw can be compared to universal tales like Romeo and Juliet, making them relatable and intriguing to a global audience.

Festivals and Cultural Events: Organizing more festivals similar to the "Mizdakhan - Sacred and Mysterious Place" or Stixiya can help immerse tourists in the local culture. These events provide a platform for experiencing the heritage and traditions of Karakalpakstan firsthand.

Art and Music: Utilizing art forms that transcend language barriers, such as ballets, musical performances, and visual arts, can effectively communicate the region's stories and cultural heritage. These mediums can attract international audiences and make the region's history accessible to a broader audience.

Digital Marketing and Social Media: Harnessing the power of digital marketing, including social media campaigns, blogs, and influencer partnerships, can increase visibility and attract a younger, tech-savvy audience. Engaging content like virtual tours, interactive maps, and user-generated content can also enhance online presence.

Collaborations with Educational Institutions: Partnering with universities and research institutions to host academic conferences, workshops, and exhibitions can draw scholarly attention and promote heritage tourism. These collaborations can also foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of the region's cultural assets.

The role of Marketing in developing touristic potential of Karakalpakstan.

Marketing plays a crucial role in making touristic places popular and visible to tourists thus it is essential to make marketing at the heart of all efforts that are being done or going to be done. These benefits that marketing can bring to this place include:

Increased Visibility: Effective marketing strategies can raise awareness about Karakalpakstan's attractions, drawing both local and international tourists. Still there are many unrevealed places in this place, which needs to be conveyed to the people with their unique stories and one way to do this is through marketing. By marking such places on global touristic routes, engaging with tourism ambassadors etc.

Economic Growth: Boosting tourism can lead to economic development by creating jobs, increasing revenue for local businesses, and attracting investments in infrastructure and services. If the pool of tourists visiting will be increased, this will create new opportunities for local people who can provide services, however, the level of service provision need to be developed according to the standards.

Cultural Preservation: Promoting heritage sites helps in preserving cultural and historical landmarks by generating funds for their maintenance and encouraging community involvement in their protection.

Community Engagement: Marketing initiatives can engage local communities, making them active participants in tourism development. This fosters a sense of pride and responsibility towards preserving their heritage.

Sustainable Development: By promoting eco and cultural tourism, marketing can contribute to sustainable development, balancing economic benefits with the preservation of natural and cultural resources.

In conclusion, leveraging marketing tools to highlight Karakalpakstan's touristic heritage can significantly enhance its appeal and visibility. Strategic storytelling, cultural events, digital campaigns, and educational collaborations are essential steps to attract tourists and ensure sustainable development of the region's rich cultural assets.

Sources:

Ким, Татьяна. (2019). Инновационное развитие сферы туризма в условиях модернизации экономики.

Mirziyoev Sh.M. Tangidiy tahlil, gat'iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik-har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik goidasi bo'lishi kerak. "O'zbekiston" NMIU, 2017. - 103 b.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining *«2022-2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi

O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida»gi Farmoni O'zbekiston Respublikasi gonun hujjatlari to'plami, 2022

Noshadi, S. (2024). "The most important wealth of Uzbekistan is its hospitable people" <https://dunyo.info/en/Eksklyuziv/sara-noshadi-samoe-glavnoe-bogatstvo-uzbekistana-eto-ego-gostepriimnyy>

Smith, M. & Robinson, M. (2006). "Cultural Tourism in a Changing World: Politics, Participation, and (Re)presentation."

Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1999). "The Experience Economy: Work Is Theater & Every Business a Stage."

World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (2022). "Tourism and Culture Synergies."